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Research Article

**ABNORMAL LIPID PROFILE IN DIABETIC PATIENTS WITH
ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE**Dr Jawaria Qureshi¹, Dr Maryam Mubeen², Dr Shahr Bano¹¹Rawalpindi Medical University²Faisalabad Medical University, Faisalabad**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020**Abstract:**

Aims and objectives: Diabetes is associated with the development of many cardiovascular diseases (CVD). The basic aim of the study was to analyze the abnormal lipid profile in diabetic patients with ischemic heart disease. **Methodology of the study:** This cross-sectional study was conducted in RIC during January 2019 to January 2020. The data was collected from 100 patients of both genders. The data were collected through randomly selected sampling technique. There were two groups of study one was suffering from diabetes and one was non diabetic patients. **Results:** The data were collected from 100 patients. The study subjects were divided: on the basis of health condition into normal, N group; non-diabetic and atherosclerotic, NA group; and diabetic and atherosclerotic, DA group. **Conclusion:** Considering the high prevalence of CVD in old age, morbidity rate can be reduced by controlling diabetes and hence, diabetes induced lipid abnormalities in these patients through different approaches, for example by changing lifestyle like dietary habits, by regular exercise and medical examination.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes is associated with the development of many cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Diabetes impairs the utilization of lipids and lipoproteins which cause diabetes induced atherogenic dyslipidemia that, is one of the most important risk factor for the development of atherosclerosis in diabetic individuals. Cardio Vascular Disease (CVD) is a leading cause of death in the world. In Sri Lanka 40 % of proportional mortality is due to CVD. South Asians are susceptible to Acute Myocardial Infarction (AMI) at an earlier age as they tend to develop higher risk-factor levels much earlier in life. Sudden cardiac death (SCD) is estimated to account for 50 % of deaths from cardiovascular causes and about half of these deaths occur in subjects who were previously undiagnosed with heart disease. Coronary artery disease is the underlying cause in 80 % of SCDs, consequently, risk factors for coronary artery disease also predispose to SCD1. Risk factors for CVD comprise dyslipidemia, diabetes, hypertension, obesity, sedentary lifestyle, smoking, alcohol, family history, menopause and advancing age. Further, homocysteine, fibrinogen, lipoprotein(a), low density lipoprotein particle size and c-reactive protein are the conditional risk factors that contribute to CVD².

Management of lipid levels as part of risk factor modification associated with CAD is usually based on lipid profiles. Several studies indicate elevated Lp(a) is independently and linearly predictive of future adverse coronary events. Lp(a) excess increase the risk of premature CAD 3–100 fold depending on the absence or presence of concomitant risk factor³. The inter-individual variability in the concentration of Lp (a) is mainly due to genetic regulation of rate of apoprotein (a) production⁴. Lp(a) promote pro-atherogenic processes by many mechanisms ie; interacting with fibrin and tissue matrix components in vessel walls, inhibiting activation of plasminogen to plasmin, inhibiting plasmin mediated activation of transforming growth factor β (TGF- β) leading to increased proliferation of smooth muscle cells and promoting inflammatory process by inducing monocyte chemotactic activity of vascular endothelial cells⁵. Blood lipid levels are modifiable risk factors for

atherosclerosis and CHD. Being hydrophobic in nature, cholesterol, cholesterol esters, triglycerides and phospholipids are transported to the other tissues in the form of lipoproteins. Major classes of lipoproteins are chylomicrons (CM), low density lipoproteins (LDL) and high-density lipoproteins (HDL), named by the site of their assembly and type of lipid and apo protein they have⁶.

Aims and objectives

The basic aim of the study was to analyze the abnormal lipid profile in diabetic patients with ischemic heart disease.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in RIC during January 2019 to January 2020. The data was collected from 100 patients of both genders. The data were collected through randomly selected sampling technique. There were two groups of study one was suffering from diabetes and one was non diabetic patients. Diagnosed cases of diabetic and non-diabetic atherosclerotic patients were included after obtaining a written consent from their care takers to take part in the study. Questionnaires were duly filled in with bio-data of the patients, clinical presentation of the illness, complete blood count record, along with available additional investigative information. Inclusion criteria were male and female, aged 45–75 years, with the history of diabetes and atherosclerosis. Exclusion criteria were subjects with the history of smoking, alcoholism, renal diseases, thyroid disorders, pregnancy or any disease.

Statistical analysis (Anova Test and Post Hoc) was performed using the SPSS software program (17.0). All results were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). As P value <0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

RESULTS:

The data were collected from 100 patients. The study subjects were divided: on the basis of health condition into normal, N group; non-diabetic and atherosclerotic, NA group; and diabetic and atherosclerotic, DA group.

Table 1: General demographic characteristics of the study population.

Subjects	Characteristics	Gender	Age groups		
			45–55 yrs	56–65 yrs	66–75 yrs
N group	Age	M	50.06 ± 0.56	60.28 ± 0.51	70.21 ± 0.52
		F	49.93 ± 0.51	53.87 ± 1.04	70.34 ± 0.54
NA group		M	50.15 ± 0.54	60.06 ± 0.52	70.21 ± 0.52
		F	53.87 ± 1.04	60.09 ± 0.49	72.21 ± 0.52
DA group		M	50.15 ± 0.53	60.06 ± 0.52	70.21 ± 0.52
		F	50.00 ± 0.55	60.09 ± 0.50	71.21 ± 0.52
N group	FBG, mmol/L	M	4.2 ± 2.9	4.3 ± 0.07	4.4 ± 0.08
		F	3.8 ± 0.06	4.5 ± 0.07	5.1 ± 0.08
NA group		M	3.9 ± 0.03	4.0 ± 0.04	5.3 ± 0.18
		F	4.2 ± 0.01	4.5 ± 0.03	5.4 ± 0.16
DA group		M	7.1 ± 0.03	8.1 ± 0.02	8.8 ± 4.8
		F	7.3 ± 0.02	7.9 ± 0.03	8.9 ± 5.2
N group	HbA1c, %	M	3.9 ± 0.56	4.0 ± 0.15	4.1 ± 0.54
		F	3.6 ± 0.51	3.7 ± 0.15	4.0 ± 0.15
NA group		M	5.6 ± 0.43	6.1 ± 0.15	6.4 ± 0.15
		F	5.7 ± 0.42	6.6 ± 0.15	6.6 ± 0.52
DA group		M	7.9 ± 0.4	8.7 ± 0.15	9.9 ± 0.51
		F	7.8 ± 0.01	8.8 ± 0.02	10.1 ± 0.55

Irrespective of statin therapy the Lp(a) concentration was not significantly different among males or females and was higher than 45 mg/dL. Variation of lipid profile values with high and low Lp(a) concentrations is stated in Table 2. The average TC and LDLc were within the normal range irrespective of Lp(a) being above 30 mg/dL (upper limit reagent kit) or more than 25 mg/dL as suggested cutoff.

Table 2: Abnormal lipid profile results in patients with DM

Lipid test	Lp(a) >30 mg/dL	Lp(a) <30 mg/dL	Lp(a) >25 mg/dL	Lp(a) <25 mg/dL
TC (< 200 mg/dL)	154.6 ± 32.2	143.3 ± 39.6	153.7 ± 34.3	142.0 ± 39.2
LDLc (< 100 mg/dL)	95.4 ± 28.9	84.4 ± 33.5	94.3 ± 30.1	83.8 ± 32.6
HDLc (> 40 mg/dL)	34.3 ± 7.4	33.0 ± 11.9	34.7 ± 9.8	31.7 ± 8.0
TG (<150)	128.7 ± 47.0	138.5 ± 77.0	131.2 ± 48.4	135.9 ± 82.6
TC:HDLc (< 5)	4.6 ± 1.2	4.6 ± 1.4	4.6 ± 1.2	4.6 ± 1.3

DISCUSSION:

Diabetic individuals are at an increased risk of CVD compared to nondiabetic individuals; therefore, diabetic subject have high mortality rate. Diabetic dyslipidemia is one of the major risk factors which contributes to atherosclerosis, one of the main forms of CVD⁷. The study analyzes the pattern of modifiable risk factor i.e., diabetes and non-modifiable risk factors like age and gender in atherosclerotic patients. Our results showed that the FBG and HbA1c levels were higher particularly in DA subjects as compared to NA. This conforms the study of Ghazanfari, *et al.* who presented that FBG and HbA1c are used as diagnostic bio-marker to separate diabetic from non-diabetic subjects⁸. The study showed that age and gender have no effect on fasting glucose level and HbA1c. However, it was found that the HbA1c value

increases in DA as well as in NA male and female groups.

The significance of this study is to highlight the effect of dyslipidemia in both males and female because it is the important parameter of atherosclerosis. The comparison of lipid profile in non-diabetic and diabetic atherosclerosis patients would enable us to maintain the health of patients by reducing cardiovascular risk. By correlating the effect of age and gender on lipid profile in these patients, it is concluded that in old age, diabetic females are more prone to dyslipidemia than diabetic males of the same age.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that comparison of lipid profile in non-diabetic and diabetic atherosclerosis patients would

enable us to maintain the health of patients by reducing cardiovascular risk. Considering the high prevalence of CVD in old age, morbidity rate can be reduced by controlling diabetes and hence, diabetes induced lipid abnormalities in these patients through different approaches, for example by changing lifestyle like dietary habits, by regular exercise and medical examination.

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